

NETWORK LOAD BALANCING WITH COMPUTATION CONGESTION DETECTION IN CLOUD DATA CENTRE

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Abstract

Cloud services are increasingly made accessible to mobile device users. Since mobile devices are generally limited in its computing resources, most of the computational tasks are being offloaded to the cloud. Offloading these computational tasks introduces another risk factor for network congestion, known as computation congestion. Congestion-aware network load balancers can help manage network congestion but they mostly focus on detecting congestion only in the links; very few has attempted to include the detection of computation congestion at the node. This research aims to characterize computation congestion in a cloud data centre and subsequently design a load balancer that would recognize computation congestion. Computation congestion characterization will be done by analyzing real workload data from Google Cluster Data Trace. The derived characteristics will then be incorporated into a congestion-aware load balancing algorithm. Lastly, the mechanism will be tested in a simulation setting of a 2-tier clos topology using traffic generated from two datasets. Performance evaluation of the mechanism will be done by analysing graphs from a network analyser.

1 INTRODUCTION

Besides link and node congestion, cloud data centres are facing another contributor of congestion, known as computation congestion [1] since more computation-intensive services are migrating to reside on cloud data centres [2]. Such migration, or computation offloading, is done to encourage users who are accessing the applications using mobile devices [3] which are usually very energy-constrained. Offloading service computation to the network, instead on clients' device, makes the service more encouraging to mobile users as it saves battery energy [4] as well as improving service availability [5].

To handle network congestion, network load balancers are employed which divert incoming traffic according to certain routing algorithm. Currently, the routing algorithm that is commonly being used is Equal-Cost Multi-Path (ECMP) routing [6], [7]. However, many researchers are proposing congestion-aware load balancers [6], [7], [8] that decides the path based on the level of loads on available links, instead of merely the distance.

Issues and Motivation. There are two issues that would like to be highlighted in this study. The first issue is the emergence of computation congestion in cloud data centres due to computation offloading. Considering that CPUs

are limited commodities, it is a possibility that congestion might happen at the CPU (bottleneck point) and affect the overall network performance.

The second issue is that the congestion metric used in network load balancers only considers link load measurements [6], [9] and does not consider the delays due to computation overloads. Network load balancers need to have knowledge of all congestion status to minimize the possibility of network congestion.

Problem statement. Since computation offloading has only been recently re-introduced into the Internet scene, not much research has been done to understand the factors that contribute to computation congestion and its characteristics. On the other hand, current research scenario is moving towards congestion-aware load balancers but most of them only employ link load measurement as the congestion indicator. As cloud data centres are being more computation-intensive, the congestion indicator in load balancers should also address computation congestion.

2 PROPOSED WORK

This research is divided into 4 stages, namely (1) identification of computation congestion metric, (2) algorithm design, (3) algorithm implementation and testing, and (4) result analysis and evaluation. The stages are rather chronological but may have some flexibility in terms of revisiting the previous stage if alterations are needed due to new circumstances.

Identification of computation congestion metric. The characteristics of computation congestion would be derived by using data clustering techniques on a publicly available cloud workload data trace, taking into account network fields such as task usage of CPU, memory, disk, and network. According to [10], only CPU and memory are constrained

resources. Thus, it is highly likely that the metrics to be chosen are task duration in seconds, CPU usage in cores, and memory usage in gigabytes.

Algorithm design. The proposed algorithm is based on a congestion-aware load balancing algorithm run in Expeditus [9]. There are basically two components of the congestion-aware load balancing, i.e. congestion monitoring and path selection. The characteristics of computation congestion at the node will be added in the local congestion monitoring component, while the load balancing component will be used per status quo with some modification to apply CPU load as the congestion metric. The information of computation load estimation is added to complement the network congestion status, which is the conceptual framework of this research. To validate the algorithm, a simple walkthrough of the sequence diagram will be conducted using a small set of test cases.

Algorithm implementation and testing. The designed algorithm will be run in a simulation environment using synthetic traffic and production data. The simulation network will be built on a 2-tier clos topology with 64 virtual servers and 4 virtual switch. Network traffic are generated using an open source network traffic generator program. Data collection of the simulation testbed will be captured using Wireshark.

One of the test dataset to be used is from Google Cluster Trace; it is a set of production-run cloud computing workload data, consisting of 12 583 machines, with approximately 600 000 jobs and 20 million tasks which was collected for 29 days. Each job is usually executed through multiple tasks, and each task runs within its isolated individual container. The container may also include several processes of the task. To ensure anonymity, certain information were concealed by randomly hashing free-text fields

and normalizing values. All records are marked with a timestamp, in microseconds, and stored as a 64-bit integer.

Result analysis and evaluation. Collected data will be analyzed using deep packet inspection tool that allows for content filtering of a pcap file. The graphical front-end has some integrated sorting and filtering options available. One of them is the Filter box at the top that allows for entering criteria for the search. The result will then be illustrated in flow completion time (FCT) graph, and compared to the other algorithms, namely ECMP, CONGA and EXPEDITUS.

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